

Status and Plans for T2K Neutrino Oscillation Analyses

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- T2K aims to address open questions in three-flavour neutrino oscillations through precision long-baseline measurements:

Which octant does θ_{23} fall in?

How are neutrino masses ordered?

Do neutrino oscillations violate CP conservation?

- T2K operates near the first oscillation maximum, enhancing sensitivity to δ_{CP} .

- T2K provides leading constraints for:

- θ_{23} and $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ from $\nu_\mu(\bar{\nu}_\mu)$ disappearance
- δ_{CP} , mass ordering and θ_{23} from $\nu_e(\bar{\nu}_e)$ appearance

- θ_{23} and $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ are precisely known; δ_{CP} poorly constrained.

$$U = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta_{23} & \sin \theta_{23} \\ 0 & -\sin \theta_{23} & \cos \theta_{23} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{atmospheric / accelerator}} \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{13} & 0 & \sin \theta_{13} e^{-i\delta_{CP}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_{13} e^{i\delta_{CP}} & 0 & \cos \theta_{13} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{reactor / accelerator}} U_{\text{solar}}$$

Super-Kamiokande (2.5° off-axis)

$$L / E \sim 295 \text{ km} / 0.6 \text{ GeV}$$

J-PARC

Near detector complex:

- INGRID (on-axis)
- WAGASCI-BabyMIND (1.5° off-axis)
- ND280 (2.5° off-axis)

Fit expected appearance spectra with near detector input

Super-K measures Cherenkov rings, ND280 measures particle tracks

Oscillation parameters extracted via joint fits to ND and FD samples using both **Bayesian** and **frequentist** statistical approaches

ND280 event rates

In MaCh3, ND constraints are applied during the oscillation fit, not beforehand

Oscillation parameters

Cross-section model

Cross sections constrained externally using near detectors (see talk tomorrow)

Measured SK event rates

Plots from EPJ C83, 782 (2023)

- Improvements on [previous oscillation analysis](#) (3.6×10^{21} POT):

- 9% increase in ν -mode data, first results with gadolinium-loaded Super-K
- Updated far detector selections for Michel electrons due to increased neutron sensitivity
- Renewed assessment of systematic uncertainties in far detector based on $\nu_e CC1\pi^+$ sample

- CP conservation is excluded with 90% confidence level for the nominal analysis; 3σ confidence interval is $[-\pi, 0.43] \cup [2.54, \pi]$.
- 18 alternative interaction and systematic model variations were tested in robustness-of-fit studies.
- The exclusion remains robust across the majority of variations; only two reduce the significance slightly below 90%.

- Subtle preference for **normal ordering**,

Bayes factor: NO/IO = 3.3

- Also subtle preference for upper θ_{23} octant,

Bayes factor: $(\theta_{23} > 0.5)/(\theta_{23} < 0.5) = 2.6$

- Precision on Δm_{32}^2 reaches 2% at the 1σ confidence limit in the frequentist analysis assuming **normal mass ordering**.

- First joint fit of T2K and Super-K datasets published in PRL:

- **T2K**: beam neutrinos, more sensitive to δ_{CP} and constrains δ_{CP} near the first oscillation maximum
- **Super-K**: atmospheric sample, probes matter effects from upward-going 2-10 GeV neutrinos, more sensitive to mass ordering and θ_{23} . Atmospheric ν provide sensitivity over a wide L/E range inaccessible to beam data
- Different energy and path length coverage breaks degeneracy

● CP-conserving values of Jarlskog invariant ($J_{CP} = 0$) excluded at:

- 1.96 σ (Frequentist)
- 2.17 σ (Bayesian, uniform prior on δ_{CP})
- 1.92 σ (Bayesian, uniform prior on $\sin \delta_{CP}$)

Plots from Phys. Rev. Lett. **134**, 011801 (2025)

- Inverted ordering excluded to 1.2σ .
- No strong preference for θ_{23} octant; T2K and SK each prefer different octants.

Plots from Phys. Rev. Lett. **134**, 011801 (2025)

- Joint fit ([published in Nature](#)) combines results from distinct detector technologies, energy spectra, and baselines:
 - **T2K**: water Cherenkov, 295 km baseline with peak energy 0.6 GeV, isolates impact of δ_{CP}
 - **NOvA**: liquid scintillator, longer and higher peak energy (810 km, 2.0 GeV), more sensitive to mass ordering

from: <https://www.kek.jp>

- See next talk by F. Cicala for more details on NOvA.

- CP -conserving values excluded at 3σ , conditional for inverted ordering (sub-plot e).
- Broader range of permissible δ_{CP} values for normal ordering (sub-plot d).
- No strong preference for θ_{23} octant in either ordering (sub-plots c, f).

Plot from Nature **646**, 818–824 (2025)

- Weak preference to **inverted ordering**; separate fits prefer **normal ordering**.
- Precision on $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ reaches 1.4% for both orderings.

Plot from Nature **646**, 818–824 (2025)

- The π^0 detector was replaced with new upstream modules in 2023:

- **Super fine-grained detector** consists of 2 million plastic scintillator cubes, lowering tracking thresholds and enhancing selection efficiency, doubles ND280 target mass to 2 t.
- **High-angle time projection chambers** facilitate full angular acceptance.
- **Time-of-flight detectors** enhance background rejection and improve sample purity.
- These improvements will directly reduce near-detector driven systematics in future oscillation fits.

- First results from ND280 upgrade already show $\sim 20\text{-}30\%$ increase in sample purity compared to pre-upgrade selections:

- Plans to include **new near detector samples** with tagged neutrons, a $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ CC γ sample, 4π solid angle samples, and to utilise WAGASCI-BabyMIND in data fits.
- **New far detector samples** under development including enhanced ν_e CC1 π^+ and NC1 π^0 .
- **Beamline upgrades** include a faster repetition rate, higher beam power (final target of 1.3 MW), and greater horn current (250 \rightarrow 320 kA).

- T2K currently provides competitive measurements of oscillation parameters, including CP-conservation exclusion to 90% confidence limit and Δm_{32}^2 measured to 1.4% precision.
- Joint fits with Super-K and NOvA both support CP-conservation exclusion, but uncertainty remains regarding the ordering choice and θ_{23} octant.
- Exciting future ahead for T2K with beamline, far detector and near detector upgrades.

Backup

The T2K Experiment

- T2K has a 295 km baseline using $\nu_\mu(\bar{\nu}_\mu)$ beam produced using **J-PARC**'s 30 GeV proton beam; protons collide with graphite target and produce hadrons, then $\pi^\pm \rightarrow \mu^\pm + \nu_\mu(\bar{\nu}_\mu)$ with magnetic horns focusing in $\nu(\bar{\nu})$ mode.
- **Near detectors** measure near-initial beam 0.28 km downstream and constrain dominant systematic uncertainties.
- **Super-Kamiokande** measures beam at first oscillation maximum, 2.5° off-axis narrows oscillation peak.

● **ND280** (2.5° off-axis, $E_\nu \sim 0.6$ GeV):

- Alternating fine-grained detectors and time projection chambers surrounded by 0.2 T magnet and electromagnetic calorimeters
- $\nu_\mu(\bar{\nu}_\mu)$ CC $Np/N\pi/0\pi/\gamma$ event rates supplied to oscillation fits
- Cross-section measurements on CH, H₂O
- Upstream modules upgraded in 2023

● **INGRID** (on-axis, $E_\nu \sim 2.2$ GeV):

- Iron and scintillator planes
- Flux measurements & beam centre monitoring
- Proton module for cross-section measurements on CH

● **WAGASCI-BabyMIND** (1.5° off-axis, $E_\nu \sim 1.1$):

- 3D grid scintillator structure
- 4π angular coverage
- Cross-section measurements on H₂O

Super-Kamiokande

- 50 kt water Cherenkov tank as T2K's far detector.
- Cherenkov ring sharpness used as main e/μ particle identifier.
- E_ν reconstructed from Cherenkov ring charge and timing assuming quasi-elastic scattering.
- Detector surrounded by photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) which detect faint light signals.
- 11,000 20" PMTs for inner detector and 2,000 8" PMTs for outer detector.
- In 2022, 0.03% gadolinium (Gd) concentration added to improve neutron tagging efficiency.
- Rich physics program for atmospheric neutrinos, supernova detection and nucleon decay searches.

6 parameters: 3 angles, $\theta_{12}, \theta_{23}, \theta_{13}$, 1 phase, δ_{CP} , 2 mass splittings, $\Delta m_{32}^2, \Delta m_{21}^2$

$$U = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{atmospheric / accelerator}} \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{\text{CP}}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{reactor / accelerator}} \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{solar}}$$

$$c_{ij} \equiv \cos \theta_{ij}, \quad s_{ij} \equiv \sin \theta_{ij}$$

Parameter	Best-fit (NO)	Uncertainty (1σ)	Comments
$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	0.308 ± 0.012	$\sim 4\%$	Solar / reactor (ν_e disappearance)
$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	0.0222 ± 0.0006	$\sim 3\%$	Reactor ($\bar{\nu}_e$ disappearance)
$\sin^2 \theta_{23}$	0.470 ± 0.015	$\sim 4\%$	Octant ambiguity persists
Δm_{21}^2 [10^{-5} eV 2]	7.49 ± 0.19	$\sim 3\%$	Solar / reactor (ν_e)
Δm_{31}^2 [10^{-3} eV 2]	2.513 ± 0.020	$\sim 1\%$	Long-baseline (ν_μ disappearance)
δ_{CP} [$^\circ$]	$\sim 212_{-41}^{+26}$	$\sim 15\%$	Weak hint of CPV ($\sim \pi/2$)
Mass ordering	Normal ordering favoured	$\Delta\chi^2 \simeq 6$	T2K-NOvA fit suggests weak IO preference

Global-fit values: NuFIT 6.0. Uncertainties quoted at 1σ ; normal ordering (NO) assumed.